

Sideroxylon inerme White Milkwood

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 10 - 15 m

Distribution:

Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, Mpumalanga and Western Cape Provinces of South Africa, Aldabra, Comoros, Kenya, Mozambique, Somalia, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zimbabwe in Africa.

Importance:

The white milkwood is a protected South African tree found along the southern and eastern coasts, where it dominates parts of the Western Cape's coastal forests. Its coppicing growth form may result in low genetic variability in isolated populations, making them vulnerable to rapid climatic change and highlighting the need for population genetic studies. The species also holds strong cultural significance, with historic gathering trees such as the "Post Office Tree" in Mossel Bay and the "Treaty Tree" in Woodstock, Cape Town.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 112.02 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.89 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.57 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 100.0% [Single: 1.9%, Duplicated: 98.1%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 22 007.81 kilobases

Contig number: 1743

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